

Fatigue Resistance of Concrete Revisited: Wide Range Data from Low-cycle to High-cycle and Influence of Aggregate on Fatigue Lifetimes

Authors' Names and Affiliations

Petr Miarka^{a,b,*}, José D. Ríos^c, Lucie Malíková^{a,b}, Vlastimil Bílek^d

^aInstitute of Physics of Materials, Czech Academy of Sciences, Žitkova 22, 616 00 Brno, Czech Republic

^bBrno University of Technology, Faculty of Civil Engineering, Veveří 331/95, 602 00 Brno, Czech Republic

^cDepartment of Continuum Mechanics and Structural Analysis, Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingeniería, Universidad de Sevilla, Camino de los Descubrimientos s/n, 41092, Seville, Spain

^dVŠB — Technical University of Ostrava, Faculty of Civil Engineering, Ludvíka Poděště 1875/17, 708 00 Ostrava-Poruba, Czech Republic

*Corresponding Author:

Petr Miarka (email: miarka@ipm.cz). Tel: +420 532 290 430

Publishing information:

Miarka P., Ríos J.D., Malíková L., Bílek V., *Fatigue Resistance of Concrete Revisited: Wide Range Data from Low-cycle to High-cycle and Influence of Aggregate on Fatigue Lifetimes*, Cement and Concrete Composites, 2026, 156, 106394, ISSN 0958-9465.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconcomp.2025.106394>.

Abstract

This paper presents the outcome of an experimental study focused on the investigation of the fatigue fracture behaviour of high-performance concrete (HPC) with granite aggregates under three-point bending. Notched beam specimens were tested under static, low-cycle, and high-cycle regimes to obtain load-CMOD responses, S-N curves, crack propagation and damage accumulation. Key parameters were derived from CMOD-controlled tests, Paris' law fitting, and a compliance-based crack growth approach. Post-test microscopy was used to characterise the fracture process zone (FPZ). The results reveal a cohesive-like law governing the cyclic damage evolution, independent of the initial notch depth. Aggregate bridging and confinement effects from large granite aggregates ($D_{\max} = 22$ mm) significantly influenced crack trajectories, delaying failure and enhancing fatigue life. Fatigue crack growth analysis identified distinct propagation phases and multiple apparent threshold stress intensity factors ($K_{I,th}$), closely linked to the material's meso-structure. The findings suggest that despite accumulated damage, final failure occurs when local conditions reach the fracture toughness of the unfatigued material. This work provides new insights into the role of aggregate type in fatigue performance and proposes a robust methodology for correlating static and cyclic fracture parameters in conventional HPC.

Keywords: Fatigue; High-Performance Concrete; S-N; Paris' law; Fracture; Damage

Copyright: ©2025. This version is made available under the CC-BY 4.0 license and all right remains to authors according to CZ/EU legislation. <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Highlights

- Fracture and fatigue properties of HPC concrete.
- Low-cycle and high-cycle fatigue tests.
- Fatigue crack growth rate based on cyclic creep curves.
- Multiple apparent threshold SIF values..

- Aggregate bridging effect enhances fatigue life.

Abbreviations

CM	cementitious materials	CTOD _c	critical crack tip opening displacement
OPC	ordinary Portland cement	SIF	stress intensity factor
FCGR	fatigue crack growth rate	ULS	ultimate limit state
FPZ	fracture process zone	SLS	service limit state
CMOD	crack mouth opening displacement	3PBT	three-point bending test
CTOD	crack tip opening displacement	LVDT	linear variable differential transformer
CMOD _{IR}	irreversible crack mouth opening displacement	LC	load case
SCM	supplementary cementitious materials		

Nomenclature

W	specimen's height [mm]	w_c	crack width [mm]
T	specimen's thickness [mm]	w_u	ultimate crack width [mm]
L	specimen's length [mm]	F_{\max}	maximum force [kN]
S	span between supports [mm]	f_c	compressive strength [MPa]
A_{lig}	ligament area [mm ²]	f_t	flexural strength [MPa]
a_0	initial notch length [mm]	r	volume density [kg/m ³]
a	crack length [mm]	G_f	fracture energy [Nm]
E_0	elastic modulus [GPa]	C, m	Paris' law coefficients
P	force [kN]	A, B	Wöhler's curve coefficients
α	relative crack length [-]	da	crack increment [mm]
K_I	stress intensity factor [MPam ^{1/2}]	dN	load cycle increment [cycle]
K_{IC}	fracture toughness [MPam ^{1/2}]	Y_{CMOD}	CMOD shape function [-]

1. Introduction

The fracture behaviour of conventional concrete, particularly under cyclic or repetitive loading, is of fundamental importance for ensuring durability, sustainability and structural safety across multiple sectors of civil engineering. From critical infrastructure such as bridges, airports and dams to everyday structures like buildings and pavements, concrete is frequently exposed to variable loading, fatigue and environmental degradation resulting from vehicle traffic, industrial machinery vibration, seismic forces, wind loading and other influences [1,2]. Modern society demands structures that are more resilient, cost-effective and long-lasting; thus, achieving a comprehensive understanding of crack initiation and fracture development under cyclical loading, and how to mitigate these phenomena, remains a key and unresolved challenge for the scientific and technological community [3,4].

Fatigue failure in concrete caused by cyclic loading is often unexpected, as it manifests as cumulative damage that is frequently overlooked. This is largely due to the fact that the primary parameters considered in structural design are the compressive and flexural strengths of the material. In such cases, fatigue is treated as a reduction in stress capacity at critical locations induced by external loading, and the service life of the structure is linked to the total number of load cycles, N [5,6]. This approach is directly related to the Ultimate Limit State (ULS), as defined by design codes such as the Eurocode [7] and ACI [8], and to the reduction in stress levels expressed as a percentage of the static strength in

compression or flexure, respectively. The stress–cycle relationship is commonly referred to as the S–N curve or Wöhler curve [9]. Structural design codes for concrete typically provide engineers with S–N curves to ensure that the structure can withstand the required service life. An example of an S–N curve adopted in Model Code 2010 [10,11] is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Model code MC2010 fatigue design recommendations.

The S–N curves presented in Figure 1 suggest overly optimistic expectations for structural service life. Even under reduced stress levels, the anticipated fatigue life ranges between 10×10^8 and 10×10^{12} load cycles, whereas Lee and Barr [12] propose a more realistic fatigue life of approximately 2×10^8 cycles for load-bearing structures. Another critical limitation is that the recommendation requires a loading frequency of 0.1 cycles/min, equivalent to 0.01667 Hz. This loading condition makes it virtually impossible to replicate the expected fatigue lives in laboratory testing environments. The exclusive use of a stress-based design approach for fatigue assessment also poses significant challenges when evaluating the Serviceability Limit State (SLS), which primarily focuses on structural deflection or the calculation of crack width, w_c . Structural deflection is directly related to stiffness, whereas the crack width w_c reflects the allowable damage within the structure. The SLS is particularly critical in prestressed concrete structures, which must demonstrate enhanced durability in aggressive environments.

To date, advances in characterising concrete fracture have focused mainly on the development and standardisation of monotonic loading experiments, among which the three-point bending test (3PBT) stands out as the most widely employed method [13–16]. Under both monotonic (static) and cyclic (fatigue) loading regimes, concrete exhibits progressive fracture behaviour marked by the nucleation, growth and coalescence of micro-cracks preceding the eventual formation of a dominant macro-crack. However, considerable distinctions exist between these two types of loading [17]. In monotonic loading, damage evolves gradually via cohesive fracture mechanisms, micro-cracking and aggregate bridging within the fracture process zone (FPZ), yet final failure tends to be abrupt once peak resistance is reached, resulting in a sudden collapse in load-bearing capacity [18]. By contrast, under cyclic loading the damage progression becomes even more gradual and complex, as existing cracks undergo repeated partial or complete opening and closure, producing cumulative degradation over an extended number of cycles before eventual fracture [19–21].

Concrete fatigue has traditionally been a complex phenomenon to study due to its inherently heterogeneous and quasi-brittle nature. Nevertheless, significant progress has been made through the adaptation of theoretical frameworks from fracture mechanics originally developed for metallic materials. In particular, a considerable body of research has employed Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics (LEFM) to characterise crack propagation in concrete under cyclic loading [22], often utilising models

based on the Paris–Erdogan law [5,23–25]. As early as the 1980s, it was demonstrated that the Paris law, which relates the crack growth rate, da/dN , to the range of stress intensity, ΔK , can be applied to concrete provided that certain material-specific modifications are introduced [26]. Among the most notable contributions is the work of Bazant and colleagues [27,28], who incorporated size-dependent effects and an effective fracture toughness contingent on crack length to model stable fatigue crack growth in concretes of varying strengths.

More recently, experimental investigations have focused on quantifying the residual load-bearing capacity of concrete under fatigue. A particularly effective means of assessing this progressive loss is through analysis of the remaining fracture energy following various levels of cyclic loading. In this context, Jia et al. [29] conducted an extensive experimental programme using 150 notched beams subjected to three-point bending fatigue. After reaching predetermined cycle counts, the beams were tested under static loading until failure to determine the residual fracture energy, $G_{F,res}$. Their results showed that $G_{F,res}$ declines sharply during the initial few thousand cycles, falling to a significantly lower fraction of the original value, before entering a slower, quasi-linear degradation phase. Remarkably, despite cumulative deterioration, unstable fatigue fracture was found to occur when the crack reached a critical toughness level very close to the static K_{Ic} . This observation suggests that the fatigue fracture threshold does not imply a drastic reduction in fracture parameters, but rather an accumulative weakening of the remaining ligament until critical conditions matching those of the unfatigued material are reached.

On another note, the type of coarse aggregate used in the mix plays a crucial role in the fracture performance of concrete [30,31]. Given that aggregate constitutes between 60 % and 80 % of the total volume [32,33], its physical properties—such as hardness, angularity, surface texture and mechanical strength, significantly influence the quality of the interfacial transition zone (ITZ) and the bridging mechanisms within the FPZ [33–35]. Recent studies have shown that concretes produced with crushed hard rock aggregates, such as granite or basalt [36], exhibit markedly higher fracture toughness. Both the critical stress intensity factor, K_{Ic} , and the critical crack-tip opening displacement, CTOD_c, increase significantly compared to concretes made with rounded gravel. In three-point bending tests, enhancements in toughness of around 30 % have been observed with granite and up to 70 % with basalt, when compared to reference concrete [37]. This improvement is attributed to the higher intrinsic strength of these rock types and their irregular geometry, which promotes stronger aggregate, matrix bonding and greater energy dissipation during fracture. It should be noted, however, that most of these studies have been conducted under monotonic loading, and there remains a limited number of investigations exploring such aggregate effects in the context of fatigue.

The literature review also reveals that a substantial portion of studies on concrete fatigue have focused on compression conditions [38] or bending [39,40], encompassing a wide range of materials: fibre-reinforced concretes [41–43], alkali-activated composites [44], and even concrete made with recycled aggregates [45–47]. Regarding the specific investigation of crack growth, most experimental campaigns focus on loading regimes around 10^4 cycles [48–50], with notable contributions such as that of Baktheer [50], who provides an extensive database on crack evolution and toughness under cyclic loading using fracture mechanics approaches including numerical modelling of cyclic failure in [51]. The practical applications of these investigations range from large-scale bending tests [52] to real structural components such as railway sleepers [53] or wind turbine foundations [54,55]. Although fatigue does not often cause immediate structural collapse, it can initiate microcracking that, as it develops over time, compromises durability and significantly reduces the service life of the structure.

The available literature on how fatigue modifies the residual fracture energy and progressively alters the FPZ remains limited, and a comprehensive understanding is still lacking regarding the influence of key parameters such as load amplitude, number of cycles, and, in particular, the type of coarse aggregate under prolonged cyclic loading [56]. Moreover, another significant gap lies in the absence of a clear and reliable correlation between static parameters, which considerably restricts the accuracy of predictive

models used in structural engineering. In addition, research specifically focused on aggregates such as granite under cyclic conditions is scarce, despite the widespread use of these materials in certain regions due to their local availability and favourable mechanical properties.

Building upon these observations, the present study aims to fill the identified knowledge gaps and provide new experimental data regarding the behaviour of high-performance concrete with granitic aggregate under cyclic loading, using standardised 3PB tests. In particular, the measurement of static fracture energy, the degradation of residual toughness with the number of cycles, and the development and transformation of the FPZ under different loading conditions are investigated. To this end, notched 3PBT specimens were tested to conduct experimental tests under three regimes: static fracture, low-cycle fatigue, and high-cycle fatigue. Special attention was paid to crack trajectories to identify the crack bridging mechanisms leading to heterogeneous behaviour under cyclic loading. This experimental campaign establishes a clear link between the increasing heterogeneity observed in cyclic tests and the role of aggregate bridging is established.

2. Material and Experimental Procedures

This section presents the composition of the high-performance concrete (HPC) mixture and provides a concise overview of the methods used for evaluating both fracture and fatigue behaviour. First, the theoretical background underlying the evaluation of fracture tests and fatigue damage analysis is introduced. The procedures for calculating fracture energy and performing inverse analysis under static conditions are described. Then, the methodology for calculating cyclic damage, including the fatigue crack growth rate (FCGR) approach and the compliance method used to assess the material constants in Paris's law, is presented in detail. Subsequently, a detailed description of the experimental setup is provided, along with the applied load cases and the geometry of the HPC specimens. Finally, the methodology for post-test damage assessment is briefly outlined. This combination of theoretical and experimental approaches provides a solid foundation for a comprehensive analysis of the complex problem of fatigue failure mechanisms in HPC.

2.1 Mixture Composition

Ordinary Portland cement (OPC) CEM I 42.5 R was used as the binder, with a constant dosage of polycarboxylate superplasticizer Glenium 300 (BASF, Germany) to ensure good workability. The water-to-cement ratio (w/c) was 0.3. Three different aggregate fractions were employed: fine sand (0/4 mm), and high-quality granite as coarse aggregates in two fractions, 4/8 mm and 8/22 mm, respectively. The mixture was prepared in a small laboratory mixer with a capacity of 0.5 m³ and directly poured into moulds. After one day, the concrete samples were demoulded, covered with polyethylene (PE) foil to prevent excessive moisture exchange with the environment, and stored in a room maintained at a controlled temperature of 20°C. The composition of the mixture per m³ is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Mix proportions of raw materials for HPC concrete per m³.

CEM I 42.5R [kg]	Water [kg]	Sand 0/4 [kg]	Aggregate 4/8 [kg]	Aggregate 8/22 [kg]	Superplasticizer (Glenium 300) [kg]
450	135	866	290	740	9

Table 1 shows the precise dosage of the mixture components. The two selected fractions of coarse aggregates were used in the mix. Mechanical properties were tested at different ages (1, 28, 91 and 365 days) according to the European standards. A summary of the measured mechanical properties is provided in Table 2.

Table 2: Measured mechanical parameters at various age.

Age [days]	Volume density ρ [kgm ⁻³]	Compressive strength f_c [MPa]	Flexural strength $f_{c,t}$ [MPa]
1	2418 ± 30	49.9 ± 0.5	-
28	2432 ± 3	91.5 ± 4.3	8.1 ± 0.4
91	2421 ± 16	90.4 ± 4	9.3 ± 1.1
365	2413 ± 18	109.6 ± 1.0	10.2 ± 0.7

Table 2 presents the measured compressive strengths obtained from 100 mm cubes [57] and flexural strengths obtained from beams with a square cross-section of 80 × 80 mm² and a length of 480 mm [58], tested at different ages. The results show relatively consistent behaviour at later ages. Additional strength measurements at 91 and 365 days provide insight into long-term strength development, which is relevant given the time-consuming nature of fatigue testing and the potential variation in concrete strength over time. The compressive strength at 365 days exhibits a further increase of approximately 20 MPa, reaching 109 MPa, confirming that the mixture meets the criteria for high-performance concrete (HPC).

2.2 Fracture Characterisation

Experimental tests were conducted to determine size-independent fracture energy by means of static three-point bending tests on prismatic specimens (specific dimensions are provided in subsection 2.2). Each specimen included an initial notch with a notch-depth-to-effective-height ratio (a_0/W) of 0.3. Three repetitions were conducted for each test configuration. During the tests, mid-span deflection was measured using a linear variable differential transformer (LVDT), while the CMOD was recorded using a clip gauge (the experimental procedure is described in further detail in section 2.5). The tests were displacement-controlled via the CMOD signal, enabling accurate capture of the post-peak softening behaviour of the material.

$$G_f = \frac{W_f}{A_{lig}}, \quad (1)$$

Additionally, an inverse analysis based on the non-linear hinge model was performed to derive the bilinear tension softening diagrams (Figure 2) [59]. The procedure was developed following the methodology proposed by Lennart, which builds upon the well-established framework of the non-linear hinge model originally introduced by Jenq and Shah [60] and subsequently adopted by numerous authors, such as Karihaloo [61], Planas et al. [62], and Roesler [63], for fracture characterization of concrete. The proposed bilinear cohesive laws presented in this study are fully compatible with discrete crack models, allowing for their direct implementation in numerical simulations aimed at accurately reproducing the fracture processes governing the structural behaviour of HPC.

Figure 2: Schematic overview of experimental data transformation to dimensionless bilinear cohesive law.

The Young's modulus was determined from three independent three-point bending tests by analysing the corresponding load–CMOD (L -CMOD) curves obtained experimentally. Following the procedure proposed by Jenq and Shah [64], the Young's modulus was calculated as the slope of the initial linear segment of each load–CMOD response, which represents the elastic behaviour of the specimen prior to crack initiation according to following expression:

$$\sigma_t(w) = \begin{cases} E\varepsilon \\ \sigma_t(w) = f_t \left(1 - \frac{w}{w_c}\right) \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The calculation accounted for the geometrical characteristics of the tested beams, including the span, cross-sectional dimensions, and notch depth. By applying this methodology individually to the three experimental load-CMOD curves, three values of Young's modulus were obtained, reflecting the variability inherent to the material and testing conditions. This experimentally derived modulus was subsequently used as a key input parameter in the fracture analysis.

2.3 Cyclic and Fatigue Damage Evaluation

In addition to using the load-CMOD curve for the evaluation of fracture energy G_f , the low-cycle fatigue behaviour of concrete can be assessed by analysing the hysteresis loops generated during cyclic loading and unloading. This approach provides deeper insight into the dissipative mechanisms associated with crack propagation and progressive material degradation. A detailed characterization of the concrete's flexural fracture response under cyclic loading, in terms of stiffness degradation observed in each load step or hysteresis loop, was performed following the methodology reported in [65,66]. A schematic representation of the recorded hysteresis loops is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Low-cycle behaviour and measured characteristics.

Figure 3 illustrates the results of a low-cycle fatigue test, represented by a typical hysteresis loop. Each loop enables fracture characterisation through the analysis of unloading stiffness degradation, which is quantified by damage parameter ω , defined as follows:

$$\omega = 1 - \frac{E_i}{E_0}, \quad (3)$$

where E_0 is the initial elastic stiffness of the material, and E_i is the stiffness corresponding to i -th hysteresis loop of the load-CMOD curve.

Additionally, the damage progression within each load cycle can be characterized by the irreversible, crack mouth opening displacement, denoted as $CMOD_{IR}$ (see Figure 3). This parameter represents the

residual crack opening that does not recover upon loading, indicating that the elastic limit of the material has been exceeded. In concrete, $CMOD_{IR}$ value arises primarily from the presence of the FPZ, rough ligament surfaces, and aggregate interlock across the crack. In contrast, for metallic materials, $CMOD_{IR}$ is attributed solely to plastic deformation.

Unlike static and low-cycle testing, the evaluation of fatigue damage lacks a standardized procedure due to the complex and not fully understood mechanisms of fatigue crack initiation in concrete. For this reasons, the S-N curve remains a practical tool for material characterization, providing a direct link to the engineering fatigue strength. Fatigue damage is evaluated using the following exponential term:

$$\sigma = AN^B \quad (4)$$

where N denotes the number of load cycles to fatigue failure, and A , B are material-specific constants typically obtained through least-squares fitting of a power-law function to the experimental data. The parameter A is associated with the static strength of the material, while B reflects the rate of progressive damage accumulation.

A more sophisticated approach to fatigue characterization is offered by the framework of linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM), which employs the power-law expression known as Paris' law:

$$\frac{da}{dN} = CK_I^m, \quad (5)$$

where C and m are the material constants associated with Paris' law, obtained from experimental data; da/dN is the fatigue crack growth rate (FCGR); and K_I is the stress intensity factor (SIF), which can be calculated as follows:

$$K_I = \frac{3PS}{2TW^2} \sqrt{\pi a_0} Y_I(\alpha), \quad (6)$$

$$Y_I(\alpha) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{1.99 - \alpha(1 - \alpha)(2.15 - 3.93\alpha + 2.7\alpha^2)}{(1 + 2\alpha)(1 - \alpha)^{3/2}}, \quad (7)$$

where P is the applied load; S , T and W are the span, thickness and width of the tested specimen, respectively; a_0 is the initial notch length; and $Y_I(\alpha)$ is the geometry shape function expressed in polynomial form as given in Eq. (7), which depends on the relative crack length $\alpha = a_0/W$. In this study, the geometry shape function was adopted from the handbook by Tada and Paris [67]. A recent study has proposed a link between the S-N curve parameter $B = 1/m$ see [40,68], which offers extended applicability for engineering fatigue assessments.

It is worth noting that both S-N and Paris' curves are influenced by several factors, including the load cycle asymmetry ratio $R = P_{\min}/P_{\max}$, loading frequency f , environmental conditions, boundary effects such as free-edge singularities [69], sequence loading[70–72], loading rate [73–75] and temperature effects [76,77].

2.4 Compliance Method

The presence of a FPZ in concrete specimens during fracture testing limits the applicability of optical crack monitoring under cyclic loading, as multiple cracks tend to develop ahead of the main crack tip. Therefore, the compliance method is employed to estimate the stress intensity factor (SIF) required for the application of Paris' law. This method relies on the progressive degradation of stiffness during cyclic loading by correlating the measured CMOD to the corresponding crack length a . The compliance, denoted as $CMOD_c$ can be calculated as follows:

$$CMOD_c = \frac{4\sigma a}{E} Y_{CMOD}(\alpha), \quad (8)$$

where σ is the applied nominal stress, a is the crack length, and Y_{CMOD} is the geometry-dependent shape function, which varies with the relative crack length a/W . In this study, the function Y_{CMOD} was again adopted from the handbook by Tada and Paris [67], and is defined as follows:

$$Y_{CMOD}(\alpha) = 0.76 - 2.28(\alpha) + 3.87(\alpha)^2 - 2.04(\alpha)^3 + \frac{0.66}{(1 - \alpha)^{1/2}} \quad (9)$$

Equations (8) and (9) follow a methodology similar to that used for the calculation of stress intensity factors (SIFs), making them suitable for crack length estimation. The approximated crack length a at a given load cycle is subsequently used in Equation (6) to calculate the SIF required for the evaluation of Paris' law parameters. The crack length estimation process is illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Workflow of compliance method for assessment of Paris' law from cyclic creep curves CMOD-N curves.

A similar methodological approach, as depicted in Figure 4, was previously employed by Bažant [48] and Le [68], both of whom focused on the size effect. However, their analyses were limited to test series involving up to ten thousand load cycles.

2.5 Experimental details

This section provides a detailed description of the specimen geometry and test setup used for the comprehensive fatigue assessment. The load cases employed to achieve the intended objectives and their influence on the experimental outcomes are discussed. Finally, the methodology used for damage assessment via optical microscopy is presented.

2.5.1 Specimen Geometry

In this experimental study, a geometry widely recognised in the research community was selected: the three-point bending test (3PBT) configuration. This setup is suitable for both static and cyclic loading,

requiring only a change in the loading protocol. The dimensions and boundary conditions of the 3PBT specimens are illustrated in Figure 5, which provides an overview of the specimen geometry.

Figure 5: The geometry and boundary conditions of the tested sample.

In particular, the prismatic concrete beams tested had a total length $L = 220$ mm, with a span $S = 200$ mm, a rectangular cross-section of thickness $T = 40$ mm and height $W = 80$ mm. Although the thickness T does not meet the requirements for a representative volume element (RVE) - which typically demands dimensions or cross-sections of 3–5 times the maximum aggregate size $D_{max} = 22$ mm - this condition is fulfilled in the crack growth direction along the specimen width W . The rectangular cross-section and dimensions were selected to accentuate the aggregate bridging effect.

The initial notch length a_0 was varied across specimens, taking values of 8, 12 and 24 mm, corresponding to relative notch depths $a_0/W = 0.1, 0.15$ and 0.3 , respectively. Shallow notches were mainly used in fatigue testing, whereas deeper notches were more appropriate for CMOD-controlled tests.

2.5.2 Experimental Test Set-up

For both static and fatigue experimental tests, a uniaxial servo-hydraulic testing machine Instron 8872 with a capacity of 25 kN (Instron, Great Britain) was used. This system allows for CMOD-controlled experiments and was employed in both the static fracture tests and the low-cycle fatigue tests. Additionally, the machine supports amplitude-controlled cyclic loading at frequencies up to 10 Hz. The experimental test setup is illustrated in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Experimental 3PBT setup, showing the notch tip and the positions of the LVDT sensors.

Data acquisition was performed using two linear variable differential transformers (LVDTs), which were mounted on the specimen to measure mid-span deflection and CMOD values. The mid-span deflection δ was recorded using an LVDT with a measurement range of ± 10 mm and linearity within \pm

60 μm (Micro-Epsilon Messtechnik, Germany). CMOD values were recorded using a high-precision COD extensometer, model Sandner EXR10-10 (SANDNER-Messtechnik GmbH, Germany), with a measuring range of 1 mm and an accuracy of $\pm 0.1\%$ and it was placed at the middle of thickness T . Both displacement measurements were synchronised with the applied load P throughout each test.

2.5.3 Experimental Protocols for Testing

As the principal aim of this investigation is to accurately characterise the behaviour of HPC subjected to a wide spectrum of loading conditions, three distinct load cases were designed to systematically evaluate the material's flexural response. These load scenarios, summarised in Table 1, constitute the experimental foundation for a comprehensive assessment of both fracture and fatigue behaviour, enabling robust analysis and interpretation of the results.

Table 1: Overview of load cases, loading conditions and main outcomes of each test.

LC name	LC type	Loading rate /frequency	LC loading	Notch length a_0/W	Result
LC1	Static fracture	0.0025 mm/min (CMOD controlled)		0.3	$L-\delta$ L -CMOD diagram G_f K_{Ic}
LC2	Cyclic /Low-cycle fatigue	0.005 mm/min (CMOD controlled)		0.15, 0.3	L -CMOD diagram $CMOD_{IR}$ Damage
LC3	Cyclic with constant amplitude/ High-cycle fatigue	10 Hz (force controlled)		0.1	S-N curve Paris' curve

Load Case Definitions:

LC1 - Static fracture test: The first load case focuses on the monotonic fracture behaviour under CMOD-controlled loading at a rate of 0.0025 mm/min until complete failure of the specimen. Key parameters obtained include maximum load P_{max} , the CMOD at P_{max} , the size-independent fracture energy G_f , and the fracture toughness K_{Ic} .

LC2 - Low-cycle fatigue test: This case evaluates the fatigue behaviour under progressive cyclic loading. The CMOD limits are incrementally increased in successive load steps, with a loading rate of 0.005 mm/min, up to a maximum CMOD of 0.5 mm or until failure. A minimum of 12 load steps was applied. Outcomes include the load–CMOD curves, damage evolution based on stiffness degradation, and the determination of the irreversible component $CMOD_{IR}$.

LC3 - High-cycle fatigue test: This case explores the long-term fatigue resistance using force-controlled loading at a frequency of 10 Hz, with a load ratio $R = P_{min}/P_{max} = 0.1$. The applied load amplitude was reduced by 10% with each new specimen, starting from 90% of the static strength, until a runout of 2×10^6 cycles was reached. This test covers both the low- and high-cycle fatigue regimes and is used to construct S–N curves and identify the Paris law parameters.

2.5.4 Post-test damage assessment

Post-test damage assessment was carried out using an Olympus DSX 1000 optical microscope (Olympus, Japan) with a maximum magnification of 1000 \times . To preserve the damaged ligament and prevent further deterioration or mortar flaking, the fractured region of the specimens was embedded in epoxy resin. Subsequently, a cross-section was cut using a diamond saw approximately 10 mm from the notch or from the visible macro-crack. The prepared specimen was then sectioned to one-third of its original thickness, aligned with the direction of crack propagation. The process of specimen preparation and damage observation is illustrated in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Schematic illustration of post-test damage analysis using optical microscopy.

Figure 7 shows two cutting planes, labelled I and II, which define the sectioning strategy. The resulting sample fragments are designated A, B, and C, allowing for precise spatial identification within the specimen. This procedure enables a detailed visualisation of the crack path and facilitates the identification of secondary effects such as crack branching, aggregate bridging, and damage mechanisms leading to failure under monotonic or fatigue loading.

3. Results and Discussion

This section provides a structured presentation of the main experimental results. First, the results of the static fracture tests and the derived bilinear softening laws are analysed, as they are essential for characterising the post-peak behaviour of the material. Subsequently, the results of the low-cycle fatigue tests are presented, focusing on damage accumulation and the development of residual crack opening. S-N curves and the Paris' law representations are then introduced to describe the fatigue life over a wide range of loading cycles. Finally, CMOD-N curves are presented to assess stiffness degradation during cyclic loading.

3.1 Fracture Behaviour

Figure 8 displays the load–CMOD responses obtained from static three-point bending tests performed on notched prismatic specimens according to LC1. The results exhibit a high degree of consistency, particularly in the initial linear-elastic phase and at the peak load, both of which are primarily governed by the elastic stiffness and tensile strength of the material. The recorded maximum loads ranged from 2.5 to 3.2 kN, corresponding to peak CMOD values between 0.15 and 0.25 mm. The post-peak descending branch reveals a pronounced reduction in the load-carrying capacity, characteristic for quasi-brittle fracture behaviour.

Figure 8: Load–CMOD curves and envelope from three static fracture tests

The shaded envelope in Figure 8 indicates moderate variability among specimens, especially in the pre-peak zones and towards the tail of the curve. The widening of the envelope at higher CMOD values reflects the stochastic nature of microcracking and the progressive degradation of the fracture process zone (FPZ), which is highly influenced by local heterogeneities such as aggregate distribution and properties. In this case, the use of coarse granite aggregates with a maximum size of 22 mm, in combination with their high strength and brittleness, directly affected crack paths and, consequently, the fracture energy.

The inverse analysis based on the non-linear hinge model (Figure 9(a)) enabled the identification of bilinear tensile softening laws (Figure 9(b)), which describe the cohesive stress transfer during crack opening as described by Eq. (2). The excellent agreement between the experimental and fitted load–CMOD curves, reflected in determination coefficients R^2 ranging from 0.993 to 0.995, validates the suitability and reliability of the results obtained. The resulting dimensionless cohesive laws exhibit similar shapes for all specimens, confirming the robustness and consistency of the identified fracture parameters.

Figure 9: Hinge model-based results: (a) experimental and fitted load-CMOD curve (Test 2); (b) bilinear cohesive laws

The moderate scatter observed in the softening branch, particularly beyond $w_1/w_u > 0.5$, is attributed to the random distribution of aggregates and the inherent heterogeneity of the concrete. These factors are known to affect the reproducibility of fracture results and are well captured by the envelope shown in Figure 9(b).

The fracture parameters obtained from the inverse analysis are summarised in Table 3. The average tensile strength was $f_t = 4.3 \pm 0.6$ MPa and the fracture energy $G_F = 133 \pm 18$ N/m, both values falling within the expected range for conventional concretes with comparable compressive strength. The bilinear shape of the cohesive laws suggests that fracture process is governed by a relatively short FPZ, with most of the energy dissipation occurring in the early stages of crack propagation, as indicated by the steep initial softening branch. The subsequent gentler slope reflects the residual stress transfer mechanisms in the damaged ligament, such as aggregate interlock and frictional effects.

Table 3: Cohesive law parameters and fracture properties derived from experimental analysis

a_1	a_2	w_1/w_u	σ/f_t	w_u [μm]	f_t [MPa]	E [GPa]	G_F [N/m]	l_{ch} [mm]
-3.4 ± 0.6	-0.4 ± 0.1	0.34 ± 0.07	0.31 ± 0.08	198 ± 22	4.3 ± 0.6	24.5 ± 2.4	133 ± 18	210 ± 57

This detailed characterisation of fracture behaviour under static loading provides a solid foundation for interpreting the cyclic loading results. Such baseline information is essential for understanding the effect of repeated loads on damage evolution and degradation, as well as for identifying the differences and similarities between the static and fatigue responses of the material.

3.2 Low-cycle Fatigue Behaviour

A comprehensive analysis of damage mechanisms under cyclic loading was conducted on concrete specimens subjected to 12 loading cycles, depending on the notch length, controlled by CMOD as described in LC2. The material response under cyclic loading is presented as load-CMOD curves, from which the shape of each loading and unloading cycle, forming characteristic hysteresis loops, can be observed.

Figure 10: Cyclic load-CMOD curves for different relative notch depths: (a) $a_0/W = 0.15$; (b) $a_0/W = 0.3$.

Figure 10 shows the results for the two studied notch-depth-to-height ratios. The experimental results shown in Figure 10 provide in-depth insight into crack propagation during each cycle loading and the progressive stiffness degradation in the post-peak phase. The shape of the load-CMOD curves reveals the energy dissipation behaviour for both notch depths (0.15 and 0.3) throughout the 12-cycle protocol.

Specimens with $a_0/W = 0.15$ exhibited more brittle behaviour after reaching peak load, as indicated by the sudden increase in CMOD during the softening phase. Conversely, specimens with deeper notches ($a_0/W = 0.3$) exhibited clearer and more regular hysteresis loops after peak load, suggesting that the material's brittleness was reduced by the increased notch depth. This reduction may be attributed to the influence of the coarse granite aggregates used (maximum size $D_{max} = 22$ mm), which promote greater crack bridging and interlocking mechanisms during fracture propagation.

The differences in cyclic response between both notch configurations become more evident when evaluating the damage parameter ω , as defined in Eq. (3). This parameter quantifies the cyclic stiffness degradation throughout the loading history. The evolution of ω for each load is presented in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Evolution of damage parameter ω for two relative notch lengths a_0/W of 0.15 and 0.3.

Figure 11 shows the evolution of the damage parameter ω during cyclic loading for specimens with different initial notch depths a_0 . A close examination of the curves (Figure 11) reveals distinct trends associated with notch depth and the remaining ligament area. Both notch depths exhibit similar damage development up to a CMOD of approximately 0.05 mm, which corresponds to the CMOD at the peak load (P_{\max}) obtained in the static fracture tests.

Beyond this point, specimens with $a_0/W = 0.3$ display higher CMOD values for the same level of damage parameter ω , in comparison to those with $a_0/W = 0.15$. This observation suggests that ω is influenced not only by the relative notch depth a_0/W , but also by the corresponding remaining ligament area A_{lig} .

Such differences in damage progression become even more apparent when analysing the irreversible crack mouth opening displacement, CMOD_{IR} , recorded at each load step and plotted in a standardised coordinate system. In this context, CMOD_{IR} is associated with the inelastic region within the evolving fracture process zone (FPZ). The resulting CMOD- CMOD_{IR} relationships are presented in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Irreversible CMOD_{IR} values for various notch depths – (a) $a_0/W = 0.15$ and (b) – $a_0/W = 0.3$.

Figure 12 presents a non-linear relationship between the irreversible CMOD_{IR} and versus the total CMOD , with the size of the inelastic component increasing with notch depth a_0 . This difference in CMOD_{IR} is attributed to the varying extent of the FPZ, which is influenced by edge effects [78] that become boundary [78] is more pronounced in specimens with deeper notches.

In shallow-notched ($a_0/W = 0.15$), the FPZ can expand more freely due to the larger remaining ligament area A_{lig} , allowing both elastic and inelastic regions to form distinctly. In contrast, for deeper notches ($a_0/W = 0.3$), the reduced ligament restricts FPZ development, resulting in a less distinguishable separation between elastic and inelastic behaviour.

Interestingly, when the coordinate system is changed from CMOD_{IR} to $\text{CMOD}-\text{CMOD}_{\text{IR}}$, a previously unrecognised trend emerges. This representation reveals a cohesive-like law that governs cyclic inelastic damage evolution. The observed relationship suggests that geometric confinement plays a key role in regulating damage accumulation during repeated loading. Figure 13 presents the experimental data and the fitted power function, which supports the existence of this phenomenon and provides a reliable model for characterising inelastic crack growth under cyclic loading.

Figure 13: Relationship between CMOD_{IR} and CMOD for both notch depths, with fitted power-law functions in valid interval.

Figure 13 shows the relationship between CMOD_{IR} and CMOD for both relative notch depths $a_0/W = 0.15$ and $a_0/W = 0.3$, along with power-law functions fitted using least-squares regression $\text{CMOD} = k \cdot \text{CMOD}_{\text{IR}}^n$. While the exponent n remains the same for both geometries, the coefficient k varies depending on the notch depth. Specifically, lower a_0/W ratios (i.e. longer remaining ligaments) result in smaller values of k , indicating that a given CMOD_{IR} corresponds to a lower total CMOD , or in other words, a smaller reversible component of the crack opening.

For specimens with short ligaments (e.g. $a_0/W = 0.3$), the FPZ interacts with the free edge, producing a geometric confinement effect that limits the energy dissipation capacity in the FPZ. Consequently, part of the damage that would normally contribute to the irreversible component CMOD_{IR} , cannot fully develop. This effect is quantitatively reflected in the exponent of the fitted power law, which takes the same value of $n = 0.582$ for both geometries.

As previously discussed, CMOD_{IR} is associated with the non-closing portion of the crack, primarily governed by aggregate interlock and the detachment of coarse particles from the cement matrix. In this context, CMOD_{IR} is related to the FPZ, which enables the formulation of power-law relationships that are independent of the initial notch tip length. The general expression for this relationship is given by:

$$CMOD = (0.815 - 0.1267\alpha) \cdot CMOD_{IR}^{0.58}, \quad (10)$$

where α is the relative notch ratio a_0/W . The relationship presented in Eq. (10) indicates that the low-cycle fatigue behaviour is governed by a cohesive law, similarly to what is observed in static fracture tests. This observation may open new avenues in the fracture assessment of concrete, potentially enabling the development of alternative constitutive models.

Although Eq. (10) may be valid only for this specific type of concrete, the robustness of the results, supported by a high coefficient of determination R^2 , provides justification for the proposed relationship. Nonetheless, the influence of the free-edge boundary on the size and development of the FPZ during cyclic loading warrants further detailed investigation through complementary techniques. For example, digital image correlation (DIC) could provide additional validation of the observed phenomena and may help to explain some unexpected results that were not initially anticipated when planning the experimental campaign [79,80].

3.3 High-Cycle Fatigue Behaviour

The assessment of the material's fatigue resistance begins with the construction of the S–N curve, which provides insight into the progressive reduction in mechanical performance under cyclic loading. The S–N representation also spans a broad range of fatigue regimes, from low-cycle to high-cycle domains. In this study, a total of 16 specimens were tested to construct the experimental S–N curve. Stresses were calculated based on the measured specimen dimensions and the applied loads using LC3. The resulting curve is shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Experimentally measured S–N curve for HPC under force-controlled loading.

Figure 14 presents the experimental results along with the evaluated S–N curve, derived by fitting the data and excluding the runout specimens (i.e. samples that did not fail before reaching 2×10^6 cycles). The data show relatively consistent behaviour in the static regime, but exhibit increasing scatter as the fatigue life approaches the runout threshold. This scatter is reflected in the relatively low coefficient of determination, $R^2=0.62$.

Notably, two specimens subjected to a maximum applied stress of $\sigma_{max} = 5.5$ MPa (labelled FAT_01 and FAT_02) displayed unexpectedly high fatigue lives of 985 and 1 092 779 cycles (or three orders of magnitude difference), respectively. These results highlight the inherent variability in high-cycle fatigue behaviour, which was not observed in static or low-cycle tests. We attribute this scatter to the influence of the coarse granite aggregate used ($D_{max}=22$ mm). When large aggregate particles are located near the notch, they promote crack bridging and increase the effective crack path length, thereby delaying fatigue

failure and extending the specimen's service life. The fitted parameters A and B from Eq. (4), obtained through least-squares regression of the experimental S–N data, are summarised in Table 4.

Table 4: Summary of fatigue parameters evaluated from the experimental S–N curve.

f_t [MPa]	A [MPa]	B [-]	R^2 [-]	σ_{fat} [MPa]	σ_{fat}/A [%]
5.745	5.759	-0.017	0.62	4.0	70

The evaluated fitting parameter A , derived from the S–N curve, closely matches the mean measured tensile strength f_t , indicating consistent and homogeneous behaviour of the material under static loading. The slope coefficient B , with a value of -0.017, aligns with previously reported results for high-performance concrete (HPC); for instance, the same value was obtained in the study by [40]. By contrast, typical values of B for normal-strength concrete ($f_c < 60$ MPa) fall in the range of -0.03 to -0.04, reflecting a more rapid mechanical degradation under cyclic loading. The relatively flat slope observed here suggests a good resistance of fatigue loading. This is further supported by the measured fatigue limit stress σ_{fat} at 2×10^6 cycles, which was found to be 4.0 MPa, representing a 30% reduction relative to the mean static tensile strength f_t . Additionally, the large scatter in fatigue performance remains evident, with fatigue limits ranging from 3.8 MPa to 4.75 MPa across the tested specimens (see empty symbols in Figure 14).

As the 3PBT specimens were instrumented with a clip gauge during the fatigue tests, CMOD–N curves were recorded for each specimen. This continuous monitoring of CMOD during cyclic loading enabled the application of the compliance method (described in Figure 4 and Eqs. (8)–(9)) to evaluate fatigue crack growth in accordance with Paris' law. This approach allows for a more comprehensive analysis, as CMOD is directly linked to the specimen's stiffness and its progressive degradation under fatigue loading. Subsequently, the experimental results provide the necessary information for the calibration of numerical models [81–84] or serve as a dataset for training neural networks [85].

Depending on the phase of the load cycle, either $CMOD_{min}$ or $CMOD_{max}$ can be used, corresponding to the minimum P_{min} and maximum P_{max} applied loads, respectively. Both values, $CMOD_{min}$ and $CMOD_{max}$, result in the computation of $K_{I,min}$ and $K_{I,max}$, minimum and maximum SIFs. Accurate calculation of the SIFs using the compliance method depends on the appropriate value of the Young's modulus E , a value of 24.5 GPa, (as listed in Table 3) was therefore used in Eq. (8). The fatigue crack growth curves derived using $K_{I,max}$ are shown in Figure 15.

Figure 15: Measured fatigue crack growth rates related using $K_{I,max}$ values from compliance-based calculations.

Each data set in Figure 15 corresponds to a single specimen selected from the S-N data set in Figure 14. A total of 10 specimens were analysed, with applied maximum stresses ranging from 5.5 MPa to 3.8 MPa. Consequently, each dataset is associated with a different $K_{I,max}$ range due to the variation in load. A closer examination of the results in Figure 15 reveals two distinct phases of crack growth: deceleration followed by acceleration, which is characteristic of brittle matrix composites [86,87]. In this analysis, $K_{I,max}$ was chosen as the reference SIF since it corresponds to the portion of the load cycle most likely to initiate and propagate fatigue cracks.

Moreover, the computed $K_{I,max}$ values span from 0.9 MPam^{1/2} to 3.2 MPam^{1/2}. These relatively high value of SIF, especially when compared to the typical fracture toughness K_{IC} of conventional concrete (ranging from 0.8 to 1.3 MPam^{1/2} [88,89]), occur near final failure, when CMOD values are elevated and the crack length exceeds $a_0/W > 0.7$.

The results in Figure 15 also indicate the presence of multiple threshold stress intensity values K_{th} , which may be attributed to variations in applied stress and the influence of coarse granite aggregates ($D_{max} = 22$ mm). The phenomenon of crack bridging becomes particularly evident when aggregate particles are located at or near the notch. In such cases, the crack is forced to propagate around the aggregate, increasing the effective crack path length and enhancing fatigue life. This difference in fatigue performance is especially noticeable in the two specimens tested at $\sigma_{max} = 5.5$ MPa, (see Figure 14), which are further examined in detail from a fracture mechanics perspective. Their corresponding fatigue crack growth rates are presented in Figure 16.

Figure 16 shows a comprehensive analysis of the FCGRs for two selected concrete specimens, progressing from raw experimental data to the derivation of Paris's law parameters. Figure 16(a-b)-(i) show the raw data, illustrating typical deceleration and acceleration phases with an identifiable apparent threshold value $K_{I,th}$ [90]. Figure 16 (a-b)-(ii) segment the crack propagation into four distinct stages (I-IV), while Figure 16(a-b)-(iii) and Figure 16 (a-b)-(iv) focus on Paris' law fits used to extract the material parameters C and m .

From the analysis in Figure 16 (a-b)-(ii), the crack propagation process can be divided into four distinct stages: **Stage I** corresponds to an *initial deceleration phase*, associated with the consumption of fracture energy during early crack formation within the cement matrix and around aggregates, commonly referred to as crack bridging. This is followed by **Stage II**, the *crack growth plateau*, which represents a near-arrest condition where propagation slows significantly due to mechanisms such as aggregate interlocking or bridging. Once the apparent threshold $K_{I,th}$ is exceeded, the crack enters **Stage III**, characterised by *stable growth* that is well-suited for Paris' law characterisation. Finally, the process culminates in **Stage IV**, defined by *unstable crack propagation* leading to the ultimate failure of the specimen.

The deceleration of fatigue crack growth observed in Stage I is attributed to the dissipation of fracture energy during crack initiation within the cement matrix and around the aggregates, a mechanism commonly referred to as crack bridging. This process leads to the appearance of an apparent threshold stress intensity factor, $K_{I,th}$. Since the crack does not completely arrest, the FCGR remains low, and the crack gradually transitions into the plateau phase identified as Stage II. This plateau is indicative of temporary crack arrest, primarily caused by aggregate bridging and, potentially, aggregate interlocking. A wider plateau, as observed in specimen FAT_02(Figure 16(b)-(ii)), suggests the presence of large aggregates near the notch tip and multiple aggregates distributed in the surrounding region. In contrast, specimen FAT_01(Figure 16(a)-(ii)) exhibits a shorter plateau, indicating less effective bridging and resulting in faster crack propagation and earlier failure.

A clear distinction between Stage III and Stage IV can be drawn from the Paris's law parameters m and C , as presented in Figure 16(a)-(iii) and Figure 16(b)-(iii). Upon entering Stage IV, both specimens, FAT_01 and FAT_02, exhibited similar FFCRs of approximately 10⁻² mm/cycle, despite experiencing significantly different SIF values. The scatter observed in Stage III for FAT_01 (Figure 16(a)-(iii)) for

suggests multiple crack bridging events occurring simultaneously, leading to propagation at a relatively constant rate. In contrast, specimen FAT_02 (Figure 16(b)-(iii)) displays isolated data points that indicate a sharp increase in FCGR, followed by a brief crack arrest, as also evidenced in Figure 16(b)-(iv). This short crack arrest precedes a phase of unstable crack growth, ultimately resulting in specimen failure. Notably, the FCGR observed in Stage IV for FAT_02 nearly doubles that of Stage III, highlighting the transition to unstable propagation.

Furthermore, having accurate knowledge of the SIF allows the estimation of crack length a at each stage of the fatigue process. Using the threshold values $K_{I,th}$ corresponding to each stage, it gives us thorough understanding, when the sample failed. Both specimens have a threshold value $K_{I,th} \approx 1.5 \text{ MPam}^{1/2}$, which corresponds to a crack length $a \approx 22 \text{ mm}$. This length coincides with the maximum aggregate size $D_{max} = 22 \text{ mm}$ used in the mixture, suggesting a direct link between mesostructural features and fracture behaviour. This correlation has previously been observed by Susmel [91] in both static and cyclic with constant amplitude loading conditions, supporting the hypothesis that aggregate size plays a critical role in defining the fracture process zone and fatigue thresholds.

The measured FCGR curves revealed multiple regions where Paris' law could be applied, allowing the evaluation of distinct sets of parameters. The resulting Paris' law parameters C and m for each stage are summarised in Table 5.

Table 5: Paris' law parameters evaluated for Stages III and IV of the fatigue crack growth curves.

Sample	N_f [cycle]	Stage III		Stage IV	
		C [mm/(cycle·MPam ^{1/2})]	m [-]	C [mm/(cycle·MPam ^{1/2})]	m [-]
FAT_01	985	-3.637	11.732	-3.804	12.57
FAT_02	1 092 779	-8.067	15.036	-14.289	29.66

The parameters are reported separately for Stage III (stable crack growth) and Stage IV (unstable growth) for both specimens. For specimen FAT_01, which failed after 985 cycles, the values of exponent m in Stages III and IV are relatively similar (11.7 and 12.6, respectively), confirming the observation from Figure 16(a) that the crack propagated at a comparable rate during both final stages.

In contrast, specimen FAT_02, which endured 1 092 779 cycles, shows a significant difference in the m values between Stage III (15.0) and Stage IV (29.7), indicating a more abrupt transition to unstable crack propagation. This behaviour is consistent with the longer plateau observed in Stage II and suggests a more effective aggregate bridging mechanism, which contributes to extended fatigue life.

Figure 16: Comparison of measured FCGRs for specimens subjected to the same applied stress but exhibiting different fatigue lives – (a) 985 load cycles and (b) – 1,092,778 load cycles.

Regarding the coefficient C , the values are -3.6 and -8.1 for specimens FAT_01 and FAT_02, respectively, which is in compliance with results present by Kirane and Bažant [26]. This difference, of nearly five orders of magnitude, further supports the conclusions drawn from Figure 16 and reinforces the link between the width of the crack arrest plateau (Stage II) and the observed fatigue life.

The observed effects of aggregate bridging and interlocking and their effects on fatigue performance were identified using a relatively simple yet effective experimental approach. However, these mechanisms warrant further investigation using advanced techniques such as DIC or acoustic emission [92]. These methods could offer a more detailed characterisation of internal damage evolution, potentially leading to improved fatigue models that incorporate the nonlinear effects of the FPZ under cyclic loading leading to numerical-based adjustments to Paris's law [93,94] or explicitly incorporate aggregate-bridging phenomena [95–97]. Furthermore, the influence of size effect [98,99] warrants dedicated investigation, which was beyond the scope of the present study.

3.4 Cyclic Stiffness Degradation

To further support the findings derived from the Paris's law analysis, CMOD- N cyclic creep curves are presented for two studied specimens, FAT_01 and FAT_02 measured by LC3. These curves serve as both experimental output and input to Paris' law formulation, as they reflect the evolution of CMOD with respect to the number of load cycles. More importantly, they offer insight into the degradation of cyclic stiffness resulting from progressive crack propagation under repeated loading [100]. The experimentally measured CMOD- N curves are shown in Figure 17.

Figure 17: CMOD- N cyclic creep curves obtained during fatigue testing for specimens FAT_01 and FAT_02.

The cyclic creep curves presented in Figure 17 compare the experimental responses of specimens FAT_01 and FAT_02 with that of the runout specimen. The results are expressed as mean CMOD values to clearly illustrate the progression of stiffness degradation during fatigue testing.

The comparison reveals that, during the initial phase of testing (up to approximately 4 cycles), the stiffness degradation in FAT_01 closely follows that of the runout specimen. Beyond this point, however, the curves diverge significantly, with FAT_01 failing at 985 load cycles. In contrast, the cyclic creep curve for FAT_02 shows consistently higher CMOD values throughout the test, indicating a larger crack opening amplitude.

This elevated CMOD in FAT_02 supports previous observations regarding aggregate bridging near the notch tip. The presence of a coarse aggregate in the initial crack path contributes to temporary crack arrest, which manifests as a plateau in crack growth. In addition to this meso-structural effect, a

geometric factor must also be considered: the width of specimen FAT_02 was $W = 70.52$ mm, FAT_01 and the runout specimen had widths close to $W \approx 79$ mm. This dimensional difference may also have influenced the CMOD response.

Interestingly, the CMOD value at which FAT_02 enters the unstable crack growth regime (≈ 0.017 mm) is comparable to that reached by the runout specimen at 2×10^6 cycles. This finding suggests that the conventional definition of the fatigue limit as a fixed cycle count is, in this case, a practical rather than fundamental limit, selected to constrain testing time in view of the demanding nature of fatigue experiments.

This behaviour highlights an important design consideration: disregarding the continued accumulation of damage in runout specimens may lead to unsafe predictions of long-term structural performance. Once again, the results underscore the need for fatigue analysis of concrete to receive greater attention, particularly through the development of reliable constitutive models capable of capturing the complex evolution of fatigue damage in quasi-brittle materials.

3.5 Damage Assessment

To validate the findings regarding fatigue crack propagation, specimens FAT_01 and FAT_02 were examined using optical microscopy following the methodology described in Figure 7. Post-test analysis of the damaged specimens enabled the localisation of aggregates within the cementitious matrix and allowed the correlation between the experimentally calculated crack lengths and the meso-structural features of the concrete. As the specimen thickness T does not meet the RVE-type criterion, the post-test crack growth analysis was carried out along the width W direction, which conforms to the required size ratio.

Each specimen was sectioned along Planes I and II, as depicted in Figure 7, providing spatial information about aggregate placement within the material. The separation between these planes was approximately 10 mm, offering a representative depth for structural interpretation.

The crack path identified in the damaged specimen was visualised under high magnification, with granite aggregates highlighted by dashed yellow lines to clearly show their location in relation to the fracture surface and the failure trajectory. It is important to note that this analysis is limited to the observation of the crack path and aggregate positioning; no attempt was made to characterise the full extent or morphology of the FPZ. The meso-structural analysis of specimen FAT_01 is presented in Figure 18.

Figure 18: Optical analysis of the crack path in specimen FAT_01 (number of cycles to failure: $N_f = 985$).

Figure 18 presents the damaged meso-structure of the specimen FAT_01, showing the identified granite coarse aggregates and the experimentally calculated crack lengths. The crack path observed in Plane I-A reveals the presence of coarse aggregate located directly in the notch region. This coarse aggregate, with its edge terminating approximately 18 mm from the specimen boundary, confirms the crack length calculated at Stage II of propagation, as shown in Figure 16(a)-(iii). Beyond this point, no further aggregates were detected in the ligament that could contribute to crack bridging or arrest mechanisms.

In contrast, the meso-structure observed in plane II-B reveals a similar aggregate in the same notch location as in Plane I-A, but with a shorter length extending into the ligament. This is followed by another aggregate approximately 25 mm from the specimen edge. However, the orientation and position of this second particle suggest that it had no significant influence on the crack path, as the fracture surface passes along its edge without signs of retardation.

similar analysis conducted on specimen FAT_02 revealed a greater number of aggregates located near the notch tip and a noticeably rougher fracture surface. These features suggest more extensive crack–aggregate interaction. The results of the meso-structural characterisation and the corresponding crack path for FAT_02 are presented in Figure 19.

Figure 19: Optical analysis of the crack path in specimen FAT_02 (number of cycles to failure: $N_f = 1\,092\,778$).

A clear distinction in the meso-structure of specimens FAT_01 and FAT_02 can be observed from Figure 19. The analysis of Plane I-A captured from sample FAT_02 reveals a coarse aggregate ($D_{\max} = 8$ mm) located directly within the notch region, followed by a second, larger aggregate ($D_{\max} = 22$ mm) and a deep intervening valley. This specific arrangement of aggregates is associated with crack arrest behaviour, as evidenced by the extended plateau observed in Stage II of the Paris' law curve (see Figure 16(b)-(ii)). Moreover, the meso-structural observations corroborate the calculated crack lengths marking the transitions from Stage II to Stage III (crack initiation), and subsequently to unstable growth in Stage IV.

The aggregate responsible for the observed crack arrest terminates approximately 38 mm from the specimen's edge and is followed by a relatively deep valley in the fracture surface. This morphology again reflects a segment of the crack path where the crack bypassed the coarse aggregate without interaction, leading to local acceleration of crack growth.

In Plane II-C, the crack trajectory exhibits a notably rough surface, with direct damage to a granite aggregate located approximately 22 mm from the specimen's edge. This damage indicates a substantial accumulation of fracture energy, ultimately sufficient to cause the crack to propagate through the aggregate, rather than around it. Such behaviour implies a temporary increase in local resistance and is consistent with the crack retardation observed during Stages III and IV of fatigue propagation, as documented in Figure 16(b)-(ii)).

When comparing static (LC1) and cyclic fatigue results (LC2 and LC3), a drastic shift in material behaviour is observed, from homogenous under static loading to highly heterogenous under fatigue conditions. The material's homogeneity, evidenced by the low scatter in measured static strengths, is lost under cyclic loading with constant amplitude, where the variability increases markedly. This straightforward yet powerful post-mortem optical analysis confirms that the observed high scatter in fatigue lifetimes can be intrinsically linked to the loading conditions, which vary in applied load.

Both static (LC1) and low-cyclic (LC2) tests were performed under CMOD-controlled conditions, which aligns with the initial hypothesis of aggregate bridging and offers valuable insight into the crack

initiation phase. In these cases, the increasing CMOD value corresponds to an extended crack initiation period during which fracture energy is steadily dissipated at a near-constant rate.

In contrast, under cyclic loading with constant amplitude (LC3), specimens are subjected to a constant stress amplitude with a load cycle asymmetry ratio $R = 0.1$, resulting in cyclic crack opening and closing at a frequency of 10 Hz. Applying constant load amplitude produces constant crack opening under which the fracture energy is slowly dissipated, as documented by low FCGR measured from Paris' law curves. It also validates the calculated crack lengths a associated with the transitions between propagation stages. More broadly, the results establish a clear link between meso-structural heterogeneity and fatigue crack behaviour, offering a mechanistic explanation. The dissipation mechanism of fracture energy during monotonic cyclic loading still remains an under-explored area and an interesting topic for explaining the significant scatter observed in the fatigue performance of quasi-brittle materials such as HPC.

Conclusions

This experimental study re-evaluated the fracture and fatigue behaviour of high-performance concrete (HPC) under a wide range of loading conditions, spanning from static to low-cycle and high-cycle regimes. The material response was investigated through notched three-point bending tests, employing varying notch lengths and. For cyclic loading, a testing frequency of 10 Hz was applied. All specimens were cast using a mix incorporating high-quality granite aggregates with a maximum size of 22 mm. The tests were conducted in CMOD controlled mode, whereas the load controlled mode was used for fatigue tests with constant amplitude. Under static loading, the material exhibited relatively homogeneous behaviour. In contrast, under high-cycle loading, its response was markedly more heterogeneous, highlighting the influence of fatigue mechanisms and meso-structural variability.

Static fracture properties were assessed using notched 3PBT specimens with a relative notch length of $a_0/W = 0.3$, which helped to reduce the apparent brittleness of the material and allowed the post-peak softening phase to be captured. Furthermore, the resulting load-CMOD curves enabled the determination of fracture energy G_f and the cohesive law parameters through inverse analysis. The material parameters were obtained with low variability and good internal consistency, confirming the reliability of the fracture characterisation.

Low-cyclic fatigue tests were performed on specimens with $a_0/W = 0.15$ and $a_0/W = 0.3$, providing insight into crack propagation under different initial ligament geometries. From these tests, the damage parameter ω was derived from the stiffness degradation, and the irreversible crack opening displacement (CMOD_{IR}) was thoroughly analysed. A power-law relationship between CMOD and CMOD_{IR} was identified, which was shown to be independent of the initial notch length and attributed to the geometric confinement effect of the free-edge boundary on the fracture process zone.

High-cycle fatigue tests were performed on specimens with $a_0/W = 0.1$, instrumented with clip gauges to monitor CMOD during sinusoidal loading. The resulting S–N curve revealed significant scatter in both the fatigue life and the runout stress σ_{fat} , emphasising the stochastic nature of fatigue failure in HPC.

From a fracture mechanics perspective, the cyclic CMOD–N curves were used to evaluate fatigue crack growth rates using the compliance method. This enabled the determination of Paris's law parameters and the correlation of meso-structural features, most notably the maximum aggregate size D_{max} , with the critical crack length a at which unstable crack growth was triggered. Moreover, the cyclic CMOD–N data confirmed progressive stiffness degradation, with the mean CMOD of the runout specimen suggesting that continued loading beyond the nominal fatigue limit of 2×10^6 cycles could eventually lead to failure. This observation questions the conventional interpretation of runout specimens as fully "safe", highlighting the importance of incorporating time-dependent damage accumulation in fatigue models.

Finally, post-test optical analysis validated the experimental findings by locating coarse granite aggregates at the notch tip and along the crack path. These observations confirmed the role of aggregate bridging and meso-structural interactions in fatigue crack initiation, retardation, and propagation, thereby offering a physical explanation for the high variability observed in fatigue performance. The results of post-test damage investigation served a direct link between meso-structural properties and the observed scatter in fatigue lifetime.

The experimental results presented within this study contributed to the understating of various damage mechanisms in concrete. However, the dissipation of fracture energy under cycling loading remains an open question, which definitely deserves more attention in future studies.

Acknowledgements

This paper was created as a part of project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004631 *Materials and technologies for sustainable development* within the OP JAK programme, co-financed by the European Union and the state budget of the Czech Republic, as well as the Czech Science Foundation under project No. 25-15755S.

J.D. Ríos acknowledges funding from the Universidad de Sevilla grant (No. SOL2024-29846) and from the Spanish Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities through a José Castillejo grant (No. CAS23/00024). Both grants supported research stays at Brno University of Technology during which the results presented in this paper were developed.

CRedit Authorship Contribution Statement

Petr Miarka: Visualization, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization, Writing – original draft. **José D. Ríos:** Visualization, Data curation, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Lucie Malíková:** Methodology, Visualization, Data curation, Writing – review & editing, Validation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis. **Vlastimil Bílek:** Supervision, Funding acquisition, Writing – review & editing.

Data Availability

The data used in this study is available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15633218>

References

- [1] R.L. Riyar, Mansi, S. Bhowmik, Fatigue behaviour of plain and reinforced concrete: A systematic review, *Theoretical and Applied Fracture Mechanics* 125 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tafmec.2023.103867>.
- [2] M. Afaghi, B.E.K. Anja, J. Arve Øverli, A Review on Fatigue Performance of Concrete Structures Part I: Loading Parameters, Current Prediction Models and Design Approaches, *Nordic Concrete Research* 68 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.2478/ncr-2023-0002>.
- [3] X. Zhao, W. Dong, B. Zhang, S. Wang, Prediction on residual flexural fatigue life of rock-concrete interface based on a deformation-controlled fatigue crack propagation criterion, *Theoretical and Applied Fracture Mechanics* 130 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tafmec.2024.104286>.
- [4] H. Chen, H. Wang, J. Zheng, Z. Wu, Residual fracture toughness and fracture energy of concrete with different strengths after fatigue loading, *Constr Build Mater* 408 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2023.133563>.
- [5] P. Miarka, S. Seitzl, V. Bílek, H. Cifuentes, Assessment of fatigue resistance of concrete: S-N curves to the Paris' law curves, *Constr Build Mater* 341 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2022.127811>.
- [6] E. Ferreira, P. Sotoudeh, D. Svecova, Fatigue life of plain concrete subjected to low frequency uniaxial stress reversal loading, *Constr Build Mater* 411 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2023.134247>.
- [7] European Committee for Standardization, Eurocode 2: Design of concrete structures—Part 1–1: General rules and rules for buildings, Brussels, 2004.
- [8] Aci, Building code requirements for reinforced concrete, (2014).
- [9] O.H. Basquin, The exponential law of endurance tests, in: n.d.: pp. 625–630.
- [10] J.C. Walraven, A. Bigaj-Van Vliet, The 2010 fib Model Code for Structural Concrete: A new approach to structural engineering, *Structural Concrete* 12 (2011). <https://doi.org/10.1002/suco.201100025>.
- [11] I.F. for S. Concrete, fib Model Code for Concrete Structures 1988, (1988).
- [12] M.K. Lee, B.I.G. Barr, An overview of the fatigue behaviour of plain and fibre reinforced concrete, *Cem Concr Compos* 26 (2004) 299–305. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0958-9465\(02\)00139-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0958-9465(02)00139-7).
- [13] K. Keerthana, J.M.C. Kishen, Micromechanics of fracture and failure in concrete under monotonic and fatigue loadings, *Mechanics of Materials* 148 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mechmat.2020.103490>.
- [14] A. Baktheer, H. Becks, Fracture mechanics based interpretation of the load sequence effect in the flexural fatigue behavior of concrete using digital image correlation, *Constr Build Mater* 307 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2021.124817>.
- [15] S. Li, D. Chen, Y. Lu, Z. Liu, Fatigue fracture characteristics of normal concrete and high ductility geopolymers bonding based on DIC technique, *Thin-Walled Structures* 196 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tws.2023.111469>.
- [16] D. Li, P. Huang, Z. Chen, G. Yao, X. Guo, X. Zheng, Y. Yang, Experimental study on fracture and fatigue crack propagation processes in concrete based on DIC technology, *Eng Fract Mech* 235 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engfracmech.2020.107166>.

- [17] S. Ray, J.M.C. Kishen, Analysis of fatigue crack growth in reinforced concrete beams, *Materials and Structures/Materiaux et Constructions* 47 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1617/s11527-013-0054-0>.
- [18] S.I. Mohammed, K.B. Najim, Mechanical strength, flexural behavior and fracture energy of Recycled Concrete Aggregate self-compacting concrete, *Structures* 23 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.istruc.2019.09.010>.
- [19] Y. Niu, H. Huang, J. Wei, C. Jiao, Q. Miao, Investigation of fatigue crack propagation behavior in steel fiber-reinforced ultra-high-performance concrete (UHPC) under cyclic flexural loading, *Compos Struct* 282 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2021.115126>.
- [20] X. Wei, D.A. Makhloof, X. Ren, Analytical Models of Concrete Fatigue: A State-of-the-Art Review, *CMES - Computer Modeling in Engineering and Sciences* 131 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.32604/cmes.2022.020160>.
- [21] X. Chen, J. Bu, X. Fan, J. Lu, L. Xu, Effect of loading frequency and stress level on low cycle fatigue behavior of plain concrete in direct tension, *Constr Build Mater* 133 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2016.12.085>.
- [22] R.O. Ritchie, Incomplete self-similarity and fatigue-crack growth, *Int J Fract* 132 (2005) 197–203. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S10704-005-2266-Y/METRICS>.
- [23] M. Jia, Z. Wu, R.C. Yu, X. Zhang, Modeling of Mixed Mode I–II Fatigue Fracture of Concrete Based on Paris Law, *Journal of Materials in Civil Engineering* 35 (2023). [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(asce\)mt.1943-5533.0004748](https://doi.org/10.1061/(asce)mt.1943-5533.0004748).
- [24] S. Seitzl, T. Thienpont, W. de Corte, Fatigue crack behaviour: Comparing three-point bend test and wedge splitting test data on vibrated concrete using Paris' law, *Frattura Ed Integrita Strutturale* 11 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.3221/IGF-ESIS.39.12>.
- [25] M. Jia, Z. Wu, X. Jiang, R.C. Yu, X. Zhang, Y. Wang, Modified Paris law for mode I fatigue fracture of concrete based on crack propagation resistance, *Theoretical and Applied Fracture Mechanics* 131 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tafmec.2024.104383>.
- [26] K. Kirane, Z.P. Bažant, Size effect in Paris law and fatigue lifetimes for quasibrittle materials: Modified theory, experiments and micro-modeling, *Int J Fatigue* 83 (2016) 209–220. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IJFATIGUE.2015.10.015>.
- [27] K. Kirane, Z.P. Bažant, Size effect in Paris law and fatigue lifetimes for quasibrittle materials: Modified theory, experiments and micro-modeling, *Int J Fatigue* 83 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2015.10.015>.
- [28] R.H. Dauskardt, M.R. James, J.R. Porter, R.O. Ritchie, Cyclic Fatigue-Crack Growth in a SiC-Whisker-Reinforced Alumina Ceramic Composite: Long- and Small-Crack Behavior, *Journal of the American Ceramic Society* 75 (1992) 759–771. <https://doi.org/10.1111/J.1151-2916.1992.TB04139.X>.
- [29] M. Jia, Z. Wu, R.C. Yu, X. Zhang, Residual fracture energy of concrete suffering from fatigue loading, *Eng Fract Mech* 255 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engfracmech.2021.107956>.
- [30] H. Cifuentes, J.D. Ríos, E.J. Gómez, Effect of mix design on the size-independent fracture energy of normal- and high-strength self-compacting concrete, *Materiales de Construcción* 68 (2018) 1–11. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.3989/mc.2018.00717>.
- [31] Z. Liu, M. Alsomiri, M. Li, X. Chen, J. Meng, Experimental investigation on the flexural behavior of coarse aggregate reactive powder concrete (CA-RPC) bridge deck, *Eng Struct* 271 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2022.114951>.

- [32] I.M. Nikbin, M.H.A. Beygi, M.T. Kazemi, J. Vaseghi Amiri, E. Rahmani, S. Rabbanifar, M. Eslami, Effect of coarse aggregate volume on fracture behavior of self compacting concrete, *Constr Build Mater* 52 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2013.11.041>.
- [33] H. Zhao, L. Zhang, Z. Wu, A. Liu, M. Imran, Aggregate effect on the mechanical and fracture behaviours of concrete, *Int J Mech Sci* 243 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmecsci.2022.108067>.
- [34] Z.P. Bažant, Size effect on structural strength: A review, *Archive of Applied Mechanics* 69 (1999). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s004190050252>.
- [35] Z.P. Bažant, J. Planas, *Fracture and Size Effect in Concrete and Other Quasibrittle Materials*, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9780203756799>.
- [36] K. Ostrowski, Ł. Sadowski, D. Stefaniuk, D. Wałach, T. Gawenda, K. Oleksik, I. Usydus, The effect of the morphology of coarse aggregate on the properties of self-compacting high-performance fibre-reinforced concrete, *Materials* 11 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma11081372>.
- [37] B. Chen, J. Liu, Effect of aggregate on the fracture behavior of high strength concrete, *Constr Build Mater* 18 (2004). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2004.04.013>.
- [38] A. Medeiros, X. Zhang, G. Ruiz, R.C. Yu, M.D.S.L. Velasco, Effect of the loading frequency on the compressive fatigue behavior of plain and fiber reinforced concrete, *Int J Fatigue* 70 (2015) 342–350. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IJFATIGUE.2014.08.005>.
- [39] J.D. Ríos, H. Cifuentes, R.C. Yu, G. Ruiz, Probabilistic Flexural Fatigue in Plain and Fiber-Reinforced Concrete, *Materials* 10 (2017) 767. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma10070767>.
- [40] P. Miarka, S. Seitl, V. Bílek, H. Cifuentes, Assessment of fatigue resistance of concrete: S-N curves to the Paris' law curves, *Constr Build Mater* 341 (2022) 127811. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CONBUILDMAT.2022.127811>.
- [41] N. Saoudi, B. Bezzazi, Flexural fatigue failure of concrete reinforced with smooth and mixing hooked-end steel fibers, *Cogent Eng* 6 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311916.2019.1594508>.
- [42] T. Cui, B. Ning, X. Shi, J. Li, Flexural fatigue behavior of hybrid steel-polypropylene fiber reinforced high-strength lightweight aggregate concrete, *Constr Build Mater* 377 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2023.131079>.
- [43] D. Gao, Z. Gu, C. Wei, C. Wu, Y. Pang, Effects of fiber clustering on fatigue behavior of steel fiber reinforced concrete beams, *Constr Build Mater* 301 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2021.124070>.
- [44] H. Šimonová, B. Kucharczyková, V. Bílek, L. Malíková, P. Miarka, M. Lipowczan, Mechanical fracture and fatigue characteristics of fine-grained composite based on sodium hydroxide-activated slag cured under high relative humidity, *Applied Sciences (Switzerland)* 11 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11010259>.
- [45] S. Seitl, P. Miarka, H. Šimonová, P. Frantík, Z. Keršner, J. Domski, J. Katzer, Change of fatigue and mechanical fracture properties of a cement composite due to partial replacement of aggregate by red ceramic waste, *Periodica Polytechnica Civil Engineering* 63 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.3311/PPci.12450>.
- [46] B.S. Saini, S.P. Singh, Flexural fatigue life analysis of self compacting concrete containing 100% coarse recycled concrete aggregates, *Constr Build Mater* 253 (2020) 119176. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CONBUILDMAT.2020.119176>.

- [47] P. Miarka, H. Šimonová, B. Kucharczyková, S. Seitl, B. Poletanovic, I. Merta, Optimisation of fine RCA content in mortar mixture based on the long-term fracture and fatigue tests, *Constr Build Mater* 481 (2025) 141371. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CONBUILDMAT.2025.141371>.
- [48] Z.P. Bazant, K. Xu, Size Effect in Fatigue Fracture of Concrete, *Materials Journal* 88 (1991) 390–399. <https://doi.org/10.14359/1786>.
- [49] Z. Bazant, W.F. Schell, Fatigue Fracture of High-Strength Concrete and Size Effect, *Materials Journal* 90 (1993) 472–478. <https://doi.org/10.14359/3880>.
- [50] A. Baktheer, H. Becks, Fracture mechanics based interpretation of the load sequence effect in the flexural fatigue behavior of concrete using digital image correlation, *Constr Build Mater* 307 (2021) 124817. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CONBUILDMAT.2021.124817>.
- [51] A. Baktheer, E. Martínez-Pañeda, F. Aldakheel, Phase field cohesive zone modeling for fatigue crack propagation in quasi-brittle materials, *Comput Methods Appl Mech Eng* 422 (2024) 116834. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CMA.2024.116834>.
- [52] S. Korte, V. Boel, W. De Corte, G. De Schutter, Behaviour of fatigue loaded self-compacting concrete compared to vibrated concrete, *Structural Concrete* 15 (2014) 575–589. <https://doi.org/10.1002/SUCO.201300085>.
- [53] E. Poveda, R.C. Yu, J.C. Lancha, G. Ruiz, A numerical study on the fatigue life design of concrete slabs for railway tracks, *Eng Struct* 100 (2015) 455–467. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENGSTRUCT.2015.06.037>.
- [54] J.A. de Lana, P.A.A.M. Júnior, C.A. Magalhães, A.L.M.A. Magalhães, A.C. de Andrade Junior, M.S. de Barros Ribeiro, Behavior study of prestressed concrete wind-turbine tower in circular cross-section, *Eng Struct* 227 (2021) 111403. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENGSTRUCT.2020.111403>.
- [55] X. Bai, M. He, R. Ma, D. Huang, J. Chen, Modelling fatigue degradation of the compressive zone of concrete in onshore wind turbine foundations, *Constr Build Mater* 132 (2017) 425–437. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CONBUILDMAT.2016.12.026>.
- [56] J. Yu, G. He, F. Zhao, L. Jia, State of the art of the fatigue behavior of plain and fiber reinforced concrete, *Shenyang Jianzhu Daxue Xuebao (Ziran Kexue Ban)/Journal of Shenyang Jianzhu University (Natural Science)* 23 (2007).
- [57] EUROPEAN COMMITTEE FOR STANDARDIZATION (CEN), EN 12390-3:2019 - Testing hardened concrete - Part 3: Compressive strength of test specimens, (2019) 1–10.
- [58] EUROPEAN COMMITTEE FOR STANDARDIZATION (CEN), EN 12390-5:2000 - Testing hardened concrete - Part 5: Flexural strength of test specimens, (2019) 1–20.
- [59] J.D. Ríos, H. Cifuentes, G. Ruiz, D.C. González, M.A. Vicente, R.C. Yu, C. Leiva, Multiscale analysis of carbon microfiber reinforcement on fracture behavior of ultra-high-performance concrete, *Eng Fract Mech* 319 (2025) 110998. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENGFRACTMECH.2025.110998>.
- [60] Y. Jenq, S.P. Shah, Two parameter fracture model for concrete, *J Eng Mech* 111 (1985) 1227–1241.
- [61] P. Nallathambi, B.L. Karihaloo, Determination of specimen-size independent fracture toughness of plain concrete, *Magazine of Concrete Research* 38 (1986) 67–76. <https://doi.org/10.1680/MACR.1986.38.135.67>.
- [62] M. Elices, G. V. Guinea, J. Gómez, J. Planas, The cohesive zone model: Advantages, limitations and challenges, *Eng Fract Mech* 69 (2001). [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0013-7944\(01\)00083-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0013-7944(01)00083-2).

- [63] J. Roesler, G.H. Paulino, K. Park, C. Gaedicke, Concrete fracture prediction using bilinear softening, *Cem Concr Compos* 29 (2007) 300–312. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CEMCONCOMP.2006.12.002>.
- [64] Y.S. Jeng, S.P. Shah, Nonlinear Fracture Parameters for Cement Based Composites: Theory and Experiments, *NATO ASI Series, Series E: Applied Sciences* (1985) 319–359. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-009-5121-1_11.
- [65] H. Horii, H.C. Shin, T.M. Pallewatta, Mechanism of fatigue crack growth in concrete, *Cem Concr Compos* 14 (1992) 83–89. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0958-9465\(92\)90002-D](https://doi.org/10.1016/0958-9465(92)90002-D).
- [66] B. Mu, S.P. Shah, Fatigue behavior of concrete subjected to biaxial loading in the compression region, *Materials and Structures* 2004 38:3 38 (2005) 289–298. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02479293>.
- [67] H. Tada, P.C. Paris, G.R. Irwin, A.S. of M. Engineers., A.S.M. International., The stress analysis of cracks handbook, 3rd ed., ASME Press : Professional Engineering Pub. : ASM International, New York, 2000.
- [68] J.L. Le, J. Manning, J.F. Labuz, Scaling of fatigue crack growth in rock, *International Journal of Rock Mechanics and Mining Sciences* 72 (2014) 71–79. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IJRMMS.2014.08.015>.
- [69] R.O. Ritchie, Mechanisms of fatigue-crack propagation in ductile and brittle solids, *Int J Fract* 100 (1999) 55–83. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1018655917051/METRICS>.
- [70] H. Becks, M. Classen, New insights into the load sequence effect: Experimental characterization and incremental modeling of plain high-strength concrete under mode II fatigue loading with variable amplitude, *Int J Fatigue* 185 (2024) 108334. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IJFATIGUE.2024.108334>.
- [71] A. Baktheer, J. Hegger, R. Chudoba, Enhanced assessment rule for concrete fatigue under compression considering the nonlinear effect of loading sequence, *Int J Fatigue* 126 (2019) 130–142. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2019.04.027>.
- [72] A. Baktheer, R. Chudoba, Experimental and theoretical evidence for the load sequence effect in the compressive fatigue behavior of concrete, *Materials and Structures/Materiaux et Constructions* 54 (2021) 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.1617/S11527-021-01667-0/FIGURES/10>.
- [73] P. Heek, P. Mark, Multiaxial and variable amplitude fatigue of concrete, *Civil Engineering Design* 1 (2019) 87–96. <https://doi.org/10.1002/CEND.201900010>.
- [74] J. Hümme, C. von der Haar, L. Lohaus, S. Marx, Fatigue behaviour of a normal-strength concrete – number of cycles to failure and strain development, *Structural Concrete* 17 (2016) 637–645. <https://doi.org/10.1002/SUCO.201500139>.
- [75] S. Schneider, R. Herrmann, S. Marx, Development of a resonant fatigue testing facility for large-scale beams in bending, *Int J Fatigue* 113 (2018) 171–183. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IJFATIGUE.2018.03.036>.
- [76] A. Baktheer, R. Chudoba, Experimental study of the interacting effects of loading rate and temperature on concrete fatigue behavior under compression, *Constr Build Mater* 458 (2025) 139466. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CONBUILDMAT.2024.139466>.
- [77] J.A. Sainz-Aja, I.A. Carrascal, J.A. Polanco, C. Thomas, Effect of temperature on fatigue behaviour of self-compacting recycled aggregate concrete, *Cem Concr Compos* 125 (2022) 104309. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CEMCONCOMP.2021.104309>.

- [78] X. Hu, K. Duan, Influence of fracture process zone height on fracture energy of concrete, *Cem Concr Res* 34 (2004) 1321–1330. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CEMCONRES.2003.12.027>.
- [79] P. Miarka, A.S. Cruces, P. Lopez-Crespo, W. De Corte, Fracture process zone development and length assessment under the mixed-mode I/II load analysed by digital image correlation technique, *Cem Concr Res* 173 (2023) 107261. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CEMCONRES.2023.107261>.
- [80] P. Miarka, A.S. Cruces, P. Lopez-Crespo, W. De Corte, On the localisation of the FPZ under a pure mode II load identified by a hybrid method, *Eng Fract Mech* 279 (2023) 109019. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENGFRACTMECH.2022.109019>.
- [81] J. Eliáš, J.L. Le, Modeling of mode-I fatigue crack growth in quasibrittle structures under cyclic compression, *Eng Fract Mech* 96 (2012) 26–36. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENGFRACTMECH.2012.06.019>.
- [82] A. Baktheer, R. Chudoba, Classification and evaluation of phenomenological numerical models for concrete fatigue behavior under compression, *Constr Build Mater* 221 (2019) 661–677. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CONBUILDMAT.2019.06.022>.
- [83] A. Baktheer, E. Martínez-Pañeda, F. Aldakheel, Phase field cohesive zone modeling for fatigue crack propagation in quasi-brittle materials, *Comput Methods Appl Mech Eng* 422 (2024) 116834. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CMA.2024.116834>.
- [84] A. Baktheer, M. Aguilar, R. Chudoba, Comprehensive Review of the Microplane Framework for Constitutive Modeling Focused on Homogenization Approaches, *Archives of Computational Methods in Engineering* 2025 (2025) 1–34. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S11831-025-10350-4>.
- [85] A. Baktheer, F. Aldakheel, Physics-based machine learning for fatigue lifetime prediction under non-uniform loading scenarios, *Comput Methods Appl Mech Eng* 444 (2025) 118116. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CMA.2025.118116>.
- [86] S. V. Kolluru, E.F. O’Neil, J.S. Popovics, S.P. Shah, Crack Propagation in Flexural Fatigue of Concrete, *J Eng Mech* 126 (2000) 891–898. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-9399\(2000\)126:9\(891\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9399(2000)126:9(891)).
- [87] J.J. Kruzic, R.M. Cannon, J.W. Ager, R.O. Ritchie, Fatigue threshold R-curves for predicting reliability of ceramics under cyclic loading, *Acta Mater* 53 (2005) 2595–2605. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ACTAMAT.2005.02.018>.
- [88] S. Seitzl, J.D. Ríos, H. Cifuentes, Comparison of fracture toughness values of normal and high strength concrete determined by three point bend and modified disk-shaped compact tension specimens, *Fracture and Structural Integrity* 11 (2017) 56–65. <https://doi.org/10.3221/IGF-ESIS.42.07>.
- [89] T. Zimmermann, D. Lehký, Fracture parameters of concrete C40/50 and C50/60 determined by experimental testing and numerical simulation via inverse analysis, *Int J Fract* 192 (2015) 179–189. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S10704-015-9998-0/TABLES/12>.
- [90] N. Pugno, M. Ciavarella, P. Cornetti, A. Carpinteri, A generalized Paris’ law for fatigue crack growth, *J Mech Phys Solids* 54 (2006) 1333–1349. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JMPS.2006.01.007>.
- [91] N. Alanazi, L. Susmel, Theory of Critical Distances and static/dynamic fracture behaviour of unreinforced concrete: length scale parameters vs. material meso-structural features, *Eng Fract Mech* 261 (2022) 108220. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENGFRACTMECH.2021.108220>.
- [92] S. Dubey, B. Kumar, S. Ray, Heterogeneity induced fracture characterization of concrete under fatigue loading using digital image correlation and acoustic emission techniques, *Int J Fatigue* 188 (2024) 108474. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IJFATIGUE.2024.108474>.

- [93] K. Kirane, Z.P. Bažant, Microplane damage model for fatigue of quasibrittle materials: Sub-critical crack growth, lifetime and residual strength, *Int J Fatigue* 70 (2015) 93–105. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IJFATIGUE.2014.08.012>.
- [94] N. Pugno, M. Ciavarella, P. Cornetti, A. Carpinteri, A generalized Paris' law for fatigue crack growth, *J Mech Phys Solids* 54 (2006) 1333–1349. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JMPS.2006.01.007>.
- [95] Z. Xiong, X. Liu, J. Li, A. Baktheer, K. Wolters, M. Feldmann, An accelerated phase-field model for high-cycle fatigue behaviour in quasi-brittle materials, *Theoretical and Applied Fracture Mechanics* 139 (2025) 105003. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.TAFMEC.2025.105003>.
- [96] S. Dubey, B. Kumar, S. Ray, Heterogeneity induced fracture characterization of concrete under fatigue loading using digital image correlation and acoustic emission techniques, *Int J Fatigue* 188 (2024) 108474. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IJFATIGUE.2024.108474>.
- [97] B. Kumar, S.K. Dubey, S. Ray, A theoretical model for the prediction of fracture process zone in concrete under fatigue loading: Energy based approach, *Mechanics of Materials* 188 (2024) 104850. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.MECHMAT.2023.104850>.
- [98] Z.P. Bažant, J. Planas, *Fracture and Size Effect in Concrete and Other Quasibrittle Materials*, *Fracture and Size Effect in Concrete and Other Quasibrittle Materials* (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1201/9780203756799/FRACTURE-SIZE-EFFECT-CONCRETE-QUASIBRITTLE-MATERIALS-ZDEN>.
- [99] S. Ray, J.M. Chandra Kishen, Fatigue crack propagation model and size effect in concrete using dimensional analysis, *Mechanics of Materials* 43 (2011) 75–86. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.MECHMAT.2010.12.002>.
- [100] Á. Mena-Alonso, D.C. González, J. Mínguez, M.A. Vicente, Size effect on the flexural fatigue behavior of high-strength plain and fiber-reinforced concrete, *Constr Build Mater* 411 (2024) 134424. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CONBUILDMAT.2023.134424>.